

BERYLLIUM FLUORIDES. PART II. FORMATION OF BERYLLIUM FLUORIDES IN SOLUTION

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Beryllium is known to be capable of combining with one or more fluoride ions to furnish several simple and complex fluorides. From conductometric titrations of the systems: $\text{Be}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-KF}$, $\text{BeF}_2\text{-KF}$, $\text{BeF}_2\text{-HF}$, and thermometric titration of HF by BeF_2 , the existence of BeF^- ion, BeF_2 (slightly dissociated), BeF_4^{2-} ion, and of H_2BeF_4 acid has been confirmed, but the existence of BeF_3^- , BeF_5^{3-} or BeF_6^{4-} ions, and of HBeF_3 acid could not be corroborated.

A search in literature shows that beryllium combines with one or more fluoride ions to furnish several simple and double fluorides :

The existence in solution of BeF^- ion, HBeF_3 and H_2BeF_4 acids was reported by Tananaev and Deichman (*Bull. Acad. Sci., U.R.S.S., Classe Sci. chim.*, 1947, 591; *Izvest Akad. Nauk, S.S.S.R., Otdel Khim. Nauk*, 1949, 144; *ibid.*, 1951, 26). Purkayastha (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 257) reported the existence in solution of BeF_2 , BeF_3^- , BeF_4^{2-} , BeF_5^{3-} and BeF_6^{4-} ions. The trifluoberyllates have been shown to be trimeric in the solid state (O'Daniel and Tscheischwili, *Naturwiss.*, 1943, 31, 209; *Jahrb. Min., Geol. Monatsh.*, 1945, 48A, 56), and are known to be non-recrystallisable from water (Simons, "Fluorine Chemistry", II, 1954, p 4, Academic Press Inc., N.Y.). These facts, thus, necessitate further investigation of the formation of trifluoberyllate ion, and determination of its degree of condensation in solution. The report of the existence of BeF_5^{3-} and BeF_6^{4-} ions requires further confirmation since the radius ratio of beryllium and fluoride ions demands tetra-co-ordination for beryllium.

The present author has investigated the formation of beryllium fluorides in solution by conductometric and thermometric titrations (Grobet and Dutoit, *J. chim. phys.*, 1921, 19, 324) and by Job's method of continued variation (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) taking conductivity as the index property.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium nitrate (Schering and Kahlbaum's) was dissolved in water. The solution on estimating for beryllium and nitrate showed the presence of basic beryllium salt, and therefore during the titrations calculated amounts of distilled nitric acid were added to prepare normal salt solutions. The ammonium and potassium tetrafluoberyllates, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ and K_2BeF_4 , were prepared in the usual way and recrystallised from water. Beryllium fluoride was prepared from ammonium tetrafluoberyllate according to Lebeau's method (*Compt. rend.*, 1898, 126, 1418). Potassium and sodium fluorides were prepared from E. Merck's reagent grade carbonate and hydrofluoric acid, and heating the products with a Meker burner for several hours. Other reagents used were of reagent grade.

The conductance of the solutions was measured with a Kohlrausch Universal Bridge, Cat. No. 7401, W. G. Pye and Co. Ltd., Cambridge, England. The conductometric titrations (Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4) were performed in a plastic vessel. The stirring was done with a polyethylene-enclosed

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magnetic stirrer. The glass stems of the two platinised electrodes were carefully covered with wax prior to platinising the electrodes. Fig. 1 depicts the results of titration of beryllium nitrate by potassium fluoride. In Fig. 2 the differences of the conductances observed in the titration of KF

FIG. 1

1. Curve I. 50 c.c. of beryllium nitrate solution (0.0179 *M* Be) [prepared by mixing 10 c.c. beryllium nitrate solution (0.08956 *M* with respect to Be and 0.1692 *M* with respect to nitrate), 0.4 c.c. HNO_3 (0.246 *N*) and 39.6 c.c. water] titrated by potassium fluoride (0.993 *M*).

Curve II. 58.8 c.c. of beryllium nitrate solution (0.03046 *M* Be) prepared in the above manner titrated by potassium fluoride (0.993 *M*).

FIG. 2

2. The differences of the conductances observed in the titration of 70 c.c. of KF (0.1042 *M*) by BeF_2 (1.827 *M*), and the sum of the conductances in the blank titrations as shown in Fig. 3, against mole ratio BeF_2/KF .

FIG. 3

3. Curve I. 70 c.c. of KF (0.1042 *M*) titrated by water.
Curve II. 70 c.c. water titrated by BeF_2 (1.827 *M*).

FIG. 4

4. Curve I. 70 c.c. hydrofluoric acid (0.1027 *M*) titrated by beryllium fluoride (1.827 *M*).
Curve II. 70 c.c. of hydrofluoric acid (0.1027 *M*) titrated by water.
Curve III. 70 c.c. of water titrated by beryllium fluoride (1.827 *M*).

by BeF_2 , and the sum of the conductances observed in the corresponding blank titrations (Fig. 3), were plotted against the mole ratio BeF_2/KF . In Fig. 4 the results of conductometric titration of hydrofluoric acid by beryllium fluoride have been shown along with the corresponding blank titrations. Conductometric titrations according to Job's method of continued variation of the systems $\text{BeF}_2 - \text{KF}$ (0.04M), $\text{K}_2\text{BeF}_4 - \text{BeF}_2$ (0.02M), $\text{K}_2\text{BeF}_4 - \text{NaF}$ (0.04M), and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4 - \text{KF}$ (0.08 M) were performed with equimolar solutions as usual, the solutions being kept in wax-coated tubes having rubber stoppers. The data of these titrations have, however, not been submitted (vide Discussion).

The thermometric titration of hydrofluoric acid by beryllium fluoride (Fig. 5) was performed with the usual precautions, hydrofluoric acid being taken in a plastic vessel which was in turn placed inside the Dewar flask contained in a thermally insulated box. The Beckmann thermometer was thinly coated with wax in such a way that there was no difficulty in measuring the change in temperature of the solution. The temperature change at a constant volume has been plotted against the volume of beryllium fluoride added.

DISCUSSION

The conductometric titration of beryllium nitrate by KF (Fig. 1) shows breaks in the curves at the Be : F ratios of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 4. These inflection points therefore correspond to the formation of BeF^+ ion, BeF_2 (slightly dissociated) and BeF_4^{2-} ions. The break corresponding to BeF_4^{2-} ion, however, is not a sharp one. The formation of BeF_4^{2-} ion has been confirmed by the conductometric titration of KF by BeF_2 (Fig. 2). These titration curves show the absence of BeF_2^- , BeF_3^- and BeF_6^{4-} ions. The conductometric titration curve (Fig. 4) obtained by titrating hydrofluoric acid by beryllium fluoride shows only one break corresponding to tetrafluoberyllic acid, H_2BeF_4 . The blank titration, viz., hydrofluoric acid by water, shows that H_2BeF_4 is a stronger acid than hydrofluoric acid.

The study of the systems : $\text{K}_2\text{BeF}_4 - \text{BeF}_2$, $\text{BeF}_2 - \text{KF}$, $\text{K}_2\text{BeF}_4 - \text{NaF}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4 - \text{KF}$, according to Job's method of continued variation taking conductivity as the index property, showed that in all these systems the conductance of the mixtures was always less than the sum of the conductances recorded with the corresponding blank mixtures, and the magnitude of the difference was found to be very small, becoming slightly higher at approximately 1 : 1 molar ratio of the reactants. The differential curves of the recorded conductances plotted against volume of any reactant showed erratic results. Hence, the reasons for not submitting these data are apparent. The fall in conductance of the mixtures from the sum of the blanks in the system $\text{K}_2\text{BeF}_4 - \text{BeF}_2$, however, showed the absence of BeF_3^- ion, the formation of which could be anticipated to result in an increase in conductance, assuming the mobility of BeF_3^- ion to be not less than that of BeF_4^{2-} ion. These results suggest that conductance being strictly not a linear property, its use in Job's method of continued variation should better be avoided (cf. Jones and Innes, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 1005).

The thermometric titration curve (Fig. 5) obtained by titrating hydrofluoric acid by beryllium fluoride showed only one break corresponding to the formation of tetrafluoberyllic acid, H_2BeF_4 , and no indication of any other fluoberyllic acids could be found. Thus, the result of corresponding conductometric titration was corroborated by a different method.

FIG. 5

60 c.c. of hydrofluoric acid (0.3103 N) titrated
thermometrically by beryllium fluoride (1.827 M).

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